

ONEST: The Middle way for Monetary Benefit Sharing in BBNJ Negotiations

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Based on the Oldham Pathway and Licence Model*

Work in progress. Updated versions may be available.

Abstract

This short note sets out a simple, inexpensive, easy to understand and use ONEST system operable in the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement – constituting a middle path to get negotiations out of a stalemate around genetic resources, digital sequence information and monetary benefit sharing that has been building over the last decade.

The problem of bringing transparency to the use and circulation of genetic resources is one that has vexed negotiations in a number of international agreements. Framing the problem solely as a legal one has contributed to delay and disagreement in the global governance of genetic resources. Here we set out a simple, inexpensive, easy to understand and use system operable in the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement that constitutes a middle way out of a stalemate that has been building over the last decade.

The **O**bligatory **N**otification and **E**lectronic **S**tandard **T**ag (ONEST) or batch identifier uses existing information systems-based infrastructure to open up a spectrum of legal obligations that can predictably support the basis of monetary benefit sharing or resource mobilization. This proposal can also form the operative basis of tiered contributions to a fund.

The Oldham Pathway is presented here in order to show how a transparency measure based on the batch identifier may or could work; in conjunction with automated systems including how it connects to the obligations of databases or repositories. Eventually, the aim would be to bring in ever greater automation in order to have a vertical and horizontal effect on legal obligations in the BBNJ Agreement. Vertical, as the batch identifier can be used for subsequent notification obligations, and horizontal as it can enable reporting and indicators on activity in areas beyond national jurisdiction overcoming a major analytical problem in distinguishing between activity inside the EEZ and ABNJ.

We invite comment on its operational feasibility from a legal and technical perspective.

The key features of the approach are as follows:

1. A cruise leader makes a straightforward notification under the Treaty
2. A batch identifier (ONEST) is automatically generated to accompany samples and is linked to appropriate use under the Treaty
3. The batch identifier is included in existing biodiversity information systems
4. The batch identifier is included in the outputs of scientific research, and data on its use can be retrieved through automated means in scientific, taxonomic, publication and patent databases
5. Companies gain legal certainty under the Treaty and may use the identifier in support of marketing and advertising
6. It becomes possible to automate the development of indicators on marine genetic resources and digital sequence information on genetic resources under the Treaty

7. A range of flexible monetary benefit sharing measures organised around payment tiers are enabled by the use of the identifier

ONEST

The **O**bligatory **N**otification and **E**lectronic **S**tandard **T**ag will comprise

- a) A human and machine-readable batch identifier (FAIR Principles)¹
- b) Use conditions linked to the identifier, setting out standard requirements for users;
- c) Integration with existing biodiversity information infrastructure to enable lightweight monitoring and reporting;

The main scenarios for notification focus on collection of samples that become accessions, that applies to the complete record. Accessions are currently already used to identify sequences by the scientific community.

Key Legal Elements:

An organisation or individual should notify (assumed to be by the principal investigator) the relevant mechanism or State Party that is legally established to receive the notification. This can be framed as a State Party obligation to notify information that has been made available to State Parties by nationals under their jurisdiction.

- a) When planning to conduct a cruise involving *in situ* collection
- b) When planning to install equipment for long term observation or collection (e.g., sea floor laboratory). The latter is distinct from a cruise in that it involves repeat visits over potentially long time periods to the same locations.

A website would be created at the Secretariat of the Treaty or equivalent consisting of:

- a. A registration form with a standard template for cruise details (existing templates could be accepted or form that standard);
- b. A standard identifier generator that would generate a unique batch identifier for that cruise (e.g., ONEST -202208023-1234) that resolves to an online hyperlink;
- c. Appropriate use to be established in Treaty language using conventional terminology found in CBD/COP/15/9 (FAIR, CARE, OECD EASD guidelines); The terms set out good data governance principles and can be automatically issued when the batch identifier is generated. Terms of use can be built on or added to, based on best practice if basic obligations are included in the Treaty language to reflect a flexible approach.
- d. The above elements can be automated programmatically using Application Programming Interfaces (APIs or web services) for easy integration with existing systems.

Chain of Events in Technical Terms:

1. The cruise organiser would complete the registration template with cruise details
2. The web form automatically generates a batch unique identifier for use uniquely by that cruise;
3. The identifier links to appropriate use under the Treaty
4. The cruise attaches the identifier as an accession number to all sample containers used for collection:

* Oldham, P and Kindness, J 2022 Sharing Digital Sequence Information. Study for the European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6557191>

¹ MD Wilkinson 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship' Scientific Data 3 160018 (2016). For an overview of FAIR principles see < <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>>

- a. Where samples in a container are later separated out from the containers, e.g., for taxonomic identification, mass spectrometry, sequencing etc. the batch identifier accompanies each separated accession in physical or digital form.
 - b. The identifier resolves to a standard online terms of use setting out standard rights and obligations as established under the Treaty and by its Governing Body.
5. The unique identifier is ingested by databases (e.g., OBIS, GBIF, INSDC) in ways appropriate for those systems and is publicly visible and searchable and accessible through Application Programming Interfaces (web services).
6. Where appropriate, database service providers will generate Document Object Identifiers (DOIs) for datasets containing the accessions carrying the identifier.²
7. Users of accessions are responsible for recording the identifier in scientific publications
8. Users of accessions are responsible for recording the identifier in patent applications in accordance with existing formal and substantive disclosure requirements. No modification to patent laws or regulations is required or envisioned.³
9. Users of accessions in products along the value pipeline may, optionally, use some form of logo on packaging to promote public awareness of the Treaty and their support for it. It is not reasonable to expect that they would include the identifier on packaging or ingredients. However, it is reasonable to imagine that companies should gain a reputational advantage from participating in the Treaty system and contributing to benefit sharing.

The Creative Commons use of standard “human readable” symbols as an alternative to the “lawyer readable” text may be attractive here.

State Parties to set out and enforce appropriate use in domestic measures (User Obligations):

- a) Set out that the accession falls under the Treaty and accessions must be deposited with collections/databases participating in the Treaty benefit-sharing mechanism
- b) Set out access terms (see the FAIR/CARE principles, Creative Commons Licences for example)
- c) Require that the unique identifier and link to appropriate use terminology is preserved on any derivative outputs (a common condition of conventional open license)
- d) State parties monitor usage through automated means supported by ‘trusted and public repositories’ and participating private databases (CBD/COP/15/9 recognises distinction between public and private databases)
- e) These data sources are programmatically used to calibrate subscription payments (the benefit sharing mechanism), through fairly broad tiers or bands.

Practical:

Rather than relying on individual users to report, monitoring for the use of the identifier would be automated programmatically using, *inter alia*, the following data sources:

- Open Alex index of 240 million scientific publications <https://openalex.org/>

² This approach was pioneered by GBIF to allow publishers of taxonomic data to identify publications where a record is used. In the case of taxonomy an individual dataset used in a publication may involve thousands or millions of records from multiple places. The minting of a DOI for datasets generated by users allows publishers to identify and report to funders. Publications citing GBIF data are publicly available at: https://www.gbif.org/resource/search?contentType=literature&literatureType=journal&relevance=GBIF_USED&peerReview=true

³ Based on the observation that over a decade of arguments about disclosure requirements at WIPO have failed to yield progress. Patent applicants will normally meet the standard disclosure requirement by providing the accession number from an INSDC database or international IDA under the Budapest Treaty. Where that accession is linked to a specimen with the treaty identifier it can be picked up using machine learning to process patent applications for identifiers (presently work in progress here: <https://github.com/poldham/accession>)

- Patent Collections (e.g., worldwide, US, European Patent Office, Patent Cooperation Treaty)
- INSDC databases (notably BioProject and BioSample databases that link samples to sequence and project records e.g., for COVID19 samples)⁴
- Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). GBIF already includes 44 million taxonomic occurrence records from OBIS. <https://www.gbif.org/network/2b7c7b4f-4d4f-40d3-94de-c28b6fa054a6>

Rather than create a new monitoring structure and potentially burdensome requirements, this approach would focus on automation to extract and summarise information on the use of the unique identifier for reporting. That is, it takes advantage of the existing and increasingly integrated digital biodiversity infrastructure to limit costs. Because no new system is created, the cost implications are marginal.

Outputs from monitoring, including for example open access repositories of Treaty related data, would be made publicly available through the clearing house mechanism.

Rollout of reporting and monitoring would require some coordination between databases and collections, but many already share data in various ways on a large scale. Hundreds of millions of records are now routinely processed using automated techniques (machine learning or artificial intelligence e.g., OpenAlex). The approach outlined above would remove the burden of reporting requirements from users and adopt a now well established 21st Century approach.

Feasibility:

A centralised web site and identifier generator is proposed (similar to Creative Commons above) using open-source software code on the basis that the number of cruises per year is likely to be limited.

However, an alternative or complementary option would be for the creation of national mirror sites that include the country code in the unique identifier, which may have additional cost implications. As such, there is flexibility (similar to the options for minting DOIs under a central authority). e.g., ONEST-UK-20220823-1234.

The Creative Commons runs an online licence generator that has been used to generate licences for billions of creative works <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility already uses a combination of unique identifiers and Creative Commons licences on over 2 billion taxonomic records including metadata on sequence records from INSDC databases (<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d8cd16ba-bb74-4420-821e-083f2bac17c2>).

Databases would continue to use existing identifiers and add this identifier in appropriate places (e.g. occurrence datasets for GBIF, most likely BioProject and BioSample databases for the INSDC).

It is important that the unique identifier for Treaty accession number is both human and machine readable - that is a human can derive useful information from ONEST-UK-20220823-1234 as can a machine.

COP Involvement:

The outline above focuses in one aspect on making Treaty related accessions Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable or FAIR (the latter through the terms of use). It may be necessary for COP to update any FAIR/CARE principles with specialised options for ABNJ.

⁴ See for example <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser/wwwtax.cgi?id=2697049>

The advantage of the 'conditions of use' model compared with measures such as legal provenance/ or certificate of legality is that it steers other users regarding requirements (is viral in this sense). An additional advantage is that billions of data items (notably 2.2 billion records at GBIF including 43 million records from OBIS) already use this approach.

It is essential that State Parties benefit-sharing requirement is elaborated prior to operation of ONEST. What is it that state parties could reasonably be expected to do without exposing themselves and individual users to onerous open ended and unsustainable obligations?

Resource Mobilization and Monetary Benefit Sharing:

The most important element of ONEST is that it allows for a wide spectrum of benefit sharing and/or resource mobilization options. The introduction of the accession number and associated conditions of use opens up other possibilities for monetary benefit sharing using a range of revenue generating measures such as predictable rates or percentages, revisiting bands or tiered payments periodically, payments for use of infrastructure with a portion going to the fund, linked to success in commercialisation and so on. ONEST can also support a number of pathways to bring transparency to the commercialization option.